

Coherently amplified ultrafast imaging in a free-electron interferometer

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Accessing the low-energy non-equilibrium dynamics of materials with simultaneous spatial and temporal resolutions has been a bold frontier of electron microscopy in recent years^{1–12}. One of the main challenges is the ability to retrieve extremely weak signals while simultaneously disentangling amplitude and phase information. Here, we present an algorithm-based microscopy approach that uses light-induced electron modulation to demonstrate the coherent amplification effect in electron imaging of optical near-fields. We provide a simultaneous time-, space-, and phase-resolved measurement in a microdrum made from a hexagonal boron nitride membrane, visualizing the sub-cycle spatio-temporal dynamics of 2D polariton wavepackets therein. The phase-resolved measurement reveals vortex–anti-vortex singularities on the polariton wavefronts, together with an intriguing phenomenon of a traveling wave mimicking the amplitude profile of a standing wave. Our experiments show a 20-fold coherent amplification of the near-field signal compared to conventional electron near-field imaging, resolving peak field intensities of $\sim W/cm^2$ (field amplitude of few kV/m). As a result, our work opens a path toward spatio-temporal electron microscopy of biological specimens and quantum materials^{13–19} – exciting yet sensitive samples, which are currently difficult to investigate.

Modulated electrons: from accelerators to microscopy

Free-electron physics has had a profound impact on many areas of science and technology, from electron microscopes and X-ray sources to microwave sources and accelerators. At the heart of all these applications lies the fundamental interaction between free electrons and electromagnetic fields^{20–22}. This interaction can be enhanced by modulating the electrons before (and in some cases after) the interaction^{23,24}. This electron modulation is key to applications such as electron radiation and electron acceleration, as recently demonstrated in dielectric laser accelerators^{25,26}.

Electron modulation can be achieved through either classical or quantum-mechanical methods, by shaping the longitudinal electron distribution or electron wavepacket, respectively. Complementing such longitudinal modulation methods are transverse modulation methods, executed using electrostatic and magnetostatic devices^{27–32}, microwave cavities³³, nanofabricated phase-masks^{34–36}, or via laser-driven interactions^{16,37–42}.

Many recent developments in laser-driven electron modulation have been inspired by research into photon-induced near-field electron microscopy (PINEM)⁴³. PINEM was originally conceived as an imaging technique realized in an ultrafast transmission electron microscope (UTEM). Nevertheless, at its core PINEM relies on a fundamental interaction: inelastic scattering of free-electron pulses by optical near-fields. This interaction allows one to reconstruct the near-field amplitudes down to single-nm spatial resolution^{1,43–48} and sub-ps temporal resolution¹². In fact, PINEM enabled a range of imaging modalities in a variety of nanophotonic and condensed matter systems, including surface polaritons^{1,12,45,49,50}, nanocavities^{46,47} and nanoscale plasma or charge distributions^{51,52}.

Apart from imaging applications, the electron-laser interaction in PINEM-type experiments has also inspired various electron modulation schemes. This modulation allows one to reconstruct the electron's quantum state^{53,54} and to extract the coherence and

decoherence times of quantum emitters^{55,56}. A notable application of PINEM-modulated electrons is to retrieve the temporal phase information of the optical field in a scheme coined free-electron Ramsey-type phase control⁵⁷. Such a scheme has been used to reconstruct the sub-cycle dynamics of THz² and optical fields^{58,59}. However, despite the wide range of applications enabled by electron modulation, this approach has never been used to amplify microscopy itself, i.e., it was not used to increase the sensitivity in near-field imaging with electron microscopes.

Here, we propose and demonstrate coherent amplification of electron imaging of optical near-fields⁶⁰, relying on optically modulated free electrons for probing the investigated sample (Fig. 1a). Conceptually, our imaging scheme can be thought of as a frequency-tunable Ramsey interferometer⁶¹ performing measurements at each point in the sample simultaneously. Thus, we dubbed this imaging scheme as Free-Electron Ramsey Imaging (FERI). We use FERI to specifically demonstrate coherently amplified measurements of polariton dynamics in a hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) flake held on a gold frame, forming a micro-drum structure supporting novel phonon-polariton wave excitations (Fig. 1b). Compared to conventional PINEM, we show that FERI yields 20-fold coherent amplification of the raw signal contrast, with further enhancement thanks to the electron-field interaction theory that underlies the algorithmic scheme. The overall enhancement enables the retrieval of an image when adopting incident intensities as low as $\sim W/cm^2$, paving the way to new kinds of microscopy experiments in scenarios that were previously beyond reach due to electron or laser dose sensitivity. Examples include quantum materials like high- T_c superconductors⁶², and even soft matter, where maximizing the signal with limited dose is essential.

Fig. 1 | Free-Electron Ramsey Imaging (FERI): utilizing electron modulation for coherently amplified microscopy of optical near-fields. (a) Conventional PINEM (top) scheme compared to FERI (bottom). Modulated electron interference enables the measurement of weaker field intensities and phase resolution, which are inaccessible using conventional PINEM with the same electron dose and laser intensity. (b) The platform in which we demonstrate the concepts of this work is a micro-drum made from an hBN membrane. A pump pulse in the mid-IR couples at the circular boundary, exciting a phonon-polariton wavepacket that propagates and interferes, resulting in a wave pattern with an amplitude profile that resembles a standing wave in a drum. (c) Waves of fundamentally different types can look similar in their amplitude profiles while having drastically different phase profiles. Conventional PINEM extracts the amplitude profile, while FERI additionally extracts the phase profile and can thus distinguish between the different wave types. For example, the amplitude profile in panel (a) resembles a standing-wave mode of a drum. However, the phase profile reveals that it is in fact not a standing wave, but a different wave phenomenon with a phase resembling that of a traveling wave. The polaritons propagate inside a 40 nm-thick layer of hBN held on top of a 10 nm-thick gold frame on a 40 nm-thick silicon nitride substrate. A circular hole with a 5 μm radius is drilled through the gold and silicon nitride.

It should be noted that recent advances in ultrafast electron diffraction and microscopy have enabled imaging of phonon dynamics^{6,63-67}. Particularly, ultrafast transmission electron microscopy has been recently applied to visualize the dynamics of acoustic phonon wave propagation in 2D materials^{6,64,65,68}. Our work takes a completely different path, investigating optical phonons hybridized with electromagnetic fields, also known as phonon-polaritons⁶⁹⁻⁷⁸. In comparison with acoustic phonons, the (optical) phonon polaritons have completely different dispersion relations, e.g., hyperbolic dispersion as in the hBN phonon polaritons that we investigate in this work. With respect to their acoustic counterparts, phonon polaritons also evolve on shorter timescales (from a few fs to a few ps), which necessitates a method like FERI to investigate their complete phase dynamics, as we demonstrate here using coherently amplified ultrafast transmission electron microscopy.

Phonon-polariton wavepackets with standing-wave profiles and traveling-wave phases

Combining the phase- and time-resolved capabilities of FERI reveals a surprising polariton phenomenon. The polaritonic wavepacket exhibits a multi-ring amplitude profile resembling a standing-wave (Fig. 1c left panels). Indeed, based on amplitude measurements alone (i.e., using conventional PINEM), the polariton could be identified as a standing wave. However, extracting the phase information from FERI reveals that the wavepacket acquires a continuous phase as it propagates, in stark contrast with a standing wave (Fig. 1c right panels). Therefore, the polariton wavepacket cannot be classified as either a conventional traveling wave or as a standing wave. This is a new and intriguing observation in an hBN phonon polariton micro-drum, which is phenomenologically reminiscent of known effects in acoustics^{79,80}. The observation of such behavior has been made possible only thanks to the phase-resolving capability of our FERI technique and warrants additional future research.

Experimental system for phase- and time-resolved near-field imaging

We realize FERI in a modified ultrafast transmission electron microscope (UTEM) (Fig. 2a). In a conventional system, a femtosecond laser pulse is split into two pulses. One pulse (pump) impinges on the investigated sample, and the other pulse (probe) is frequency-up-converted into a UV pulse, which photo-emits an electron pulse from the cathode. Together, such a system implements a *pump-probe* scheme with an electron as the probe. In contrast, in our modified system, the pump pulse is split into two pulses, as shown in Fig. 2a. Specifically for the experiments shown here, the pulse is frequency-down-converted to the mid-IR using difference frequency generation (DFG) before being split. The first pump pulse impinges on the investigated sample, while the second pump pulse does not interact with the sample, and instead modulates the electron before that electron probes the sample (the reference and sample order can be changed with similar outcomes). Together, the modified system implements a *pump-pump-probe* scheme, with the electron as the probe. Variants of this scheme were realized in transmission electron microscopes under different constraints, for example, using separate light-coupling ports for continuous wave operation^{59,81} or combined into a single port for pulsed operations, splitting the two points of interaction⁵⁷, or keeping them together^{49,82}.

Our specially designed microscope component, called the *photonic electron modulator* (PELM, see Extended Data Figure 2), enables independent tunability of the two pulses in two separate light-coupling ports, controlling their relative delay, intensity, and polarization, as well as other options (described in Methods M2). Specifically, the electron modulation is implemented by a flat Al-coated Si₃N₄ membrane, which is tilted at an angle of 41° with respect to the electron propagation direction to ensure transverse electron-light phase matching. The electrons penetrate through this membrane simultaneously with the laser pulse impinging on it. The flat membrane acts as a light-reflecting mirror, providing the reference interaction in

Fig. 2a, while also being relatively electron-transparent to allow further interaction with our micro-drum.

Fig. 2 | Time- and phase-resolved imaging of polariton wavepackets. (a) A schematic of the free-electron Ramsey imaging (FERI) scheme: splitting a femtosecond laser pulse to three parts, enabling both ultrafast time-resolved and phase-resolved imaging. Two delay stages are used to control the timing of the laser pulses with respect to the electron pulse. (b1) **Time-resolved imaging** presenting selected raw PINEM data frames at different time delays (full data in movie SM1 and SM2). (b2) The polariton wavepacket dynamics is presented in a map where the propagation axis represents the dynamics along the radius, averaged along a semicircle. The polariton wavepacket propagates with a group velocity of $v_g \approx c/200$, marked by a red dashed arrow. The dislocated intensity peaks along the dashed line indicate that the polariton wavepacket “hop” over certain radii of low intensity. This behavior is not expected for conventional traveling waves that propagate continuously, and not expected for conventional standing waves that do not propagate. This behavior is consistent with the observation from Fig. 1 about the polariton wavepacket, showing it to have a simultaneous standing-wave amplitude and traveling-wave phase profiles. (c1) **Phase-resolved imaging** presenting selected raw FERI data frames at different sub-cycle delays (full data in movie SM3-5), corresponding to different relative phases between the modulation and sample excitation. (c2) Algorithm-aided reconstruction of the amplitude and phase profiles from the raw FERI data frames using all phases. The phase-scan is performed around a time delay of 2 ps, marked by the orange arrow in panel (b2).

Free-electron Ramsey imaging (FERI): concept and results

Our FERI experiment extends on previous works^{49,57,59,81,82} by one important development: *coherent amplification of electron imaging*. All the above-mentioned modified

ultrafast transmission electron microscopes provide a *controllable phase relation* between the electron modulation and the induced near-field on the investigated sample (this is possible because both pump pulses were split from the same laser pulse). Our demonstration of coherently amplified electron imaging requires an additional development, which can be summarized in two stages: (1) Acquiring raw modulated-electron images, by uniformly scanning over the relative phase. (2) Applying a reconstruction algorithm on the raw images, extracting high-contrast phase and amplitude of the sample near-field.

After its interaction with the sample, each modulated electron can be characterized by measuring its electron energy spectrum, which depends on the sample near-field and its phase relative to the reference interaction. We specifically use electron energy filtering on the electron image (Methods M2). This way, for each choice of modulation phase, the raw electron image provides different information about the near-field at the sample. By combining the raw images (Methods M6), our algorithm yields the phase and the amplified contrast in the amplitude profile, meaning that weaker fields can be reconstructed with the same electron dose. For example, Fig. 1a compares two images acquired with the same total electron dose and same field intensity on the sample – showing the advantage of FERI over conventional PINEM, with a 20-fold increase in the resulting signal contrast.

At every pixel, our scheme is analogous to Ramsey interferometry in atomic physics⁸³ or to homodyne detection in optics⁸⁴. However, this analogy is not precise. Only for special cases, depending on the interaction strength and on the distance between the modulation stage and the sample, our algorithm reproduces the regime where the Radon transform is used in conventional homodyne detection⁸⁵. But for the general case, our algorithm goes beyond the Radon transform⁸⁶. This more general case is necessary for our experiment.

Next, we apply FERI to investigate phonon-polariton wavepackets in hBN, and measure their spatio-temporal group and phase dynamics. Fig. 2(b1) illustrates the wavepacket

propagation from the Au edge of the micro-drum towards its center (a radial half-circle profile of the movies SM1 and SM2 in the Supplementary Information). The slope of the dashed red arrow in Fig. 2(b2) corresponds to the group velocity of the excited wavepacket which is measured to be $v_g \approx c/200$. By using modulated electrons and by performing a sub-cycle delay scan between the two points of interaction, the *spatio-temporal phase* dynamics of the phonon-polariton wavepacket is retrieved (utilizing an optimization process).

A peculiar feature of the propagation of the polariton wavepacket dynamics is highlighted in Fig. 2c, whereas a line profile averaged along the radius of the semicircle indicates the wavepacket propagation. Low electron counts over the dashed red line indicate that the polariton wavepacket “hops” over certain positions in space. This hopping behavior is not expected for conventional wavepackets and is consistent with the observation from Fig. 1 about the polariton wavepacket having simultaneously a standing-wave-like amplitude profile and a traveling-wave-like phase accumulation.

Sub-cycle dynamics of polariton wavepackets: resolving a vortex-anti-vortex pair

Figure 3a depicts the phase profiles for different excitation wavelengths, each retrieved from a scan of sub-cycle time delays on the modulated electrons, as shown in Fig. 2c. These phase profiles provide a direct measurement of the phonon-polariton wavenumber. We extract the wavenumbers from the inverse distance over which the phase of the wavepacket accumulates 2π , and compare them with theory in Fig. 3b (black circles on top of the theoretical dispersion of hBN phonon polaritons).

The phase-reconstruction capability of FERI enables to pinpoint another intriguing phonon-polariton phenomenon. We show, for the first time in PINEM and generally in electron microscopy, the coexistence of vortex-anti-vortex singularities at the nodal point located in the center of the micro-drum wave (Fig. 3c). This occurrence is a consequence of symmetry

breaking, splitting the original point of zero-amplitude and no orbital angular momentum into a pair of polariton vortices of opposite chirality⁸⁷. We note that vortices have been previously observed in conventional PINEM⁵⁰, but identifying the vortex chirality is only made possible in FERI.

Fig. 3 | Intrinsic phonon-polariton properties extracted via FERI: direct measurement of the polariton phase velocity and identification of a pair of vortex and anti-vortex. (a) FERI phase-reconstruction for different wavelengths. (b) We use the distance between consecutive equal-phase circles for direct extraction of the polariton's wavenumber (and phase velocity). The dispersion relation of phonon-polaritons in hBN, with circles marking the extracted wavenumbers. (c-d) Zoom-in on a phonon-polariton phase profile portrays that the nodal point at the center of the micro-drum wave is comprised of a vortex-anti-vortex pair, an inevitable result of symmetry breaking in the system⁸⁷. By extracting the exact phase, FERI enables measuring the chirality of each vortex.

Coherent contrast amplification of near-field electron imaging

In this section, we describe the algorithm used in FERI and quantify the resulting coherent amplification of the electron image contrast (defined as the difference between upper and lower tenth percentile of the signal). The signal is normalized by having the same electron dose on the sample in all measurements. Figure 4a presents the contrast values extracted from measurements of FERI in different areas of the image that have different field intensities (the corresponding values of the signal shown in the table were extracted from

the reconstruction). In each region, we choose the relative phase in FERI such that maximal contrast is achieved. In all cases, the contrast is larger than the contrast in conventional PINEM. Comparison of the raw data from FERI and PINEM in Fig. 4a already shows the enhanced contrast by coherent amplification. It is interesting to note that artifacts that smear the details around the center of the PINEM image vanish in the FERI image, although it is acquired over an acquisition time shorter by a factor of 21. Near the center of the sample, where the fields are most intense, the PINEM image is saturated, possibly explaining the disagreement with the theoretical values. Yet, the contrasts ratios correspond qualitatively to the theory in Fig. 4b. In some areas of the sample, the amplification factor is on the order of 20 or more, exemplifying the power of the coherent amplification.

Fig. 4 | Prospects of FERI for precision measurements of weak fields, and comparison between the classical and quantum regimes. (a) Coherent amplification of electron imaging, showing the contrast amplification in different regions of the sample with different maximal values of g_s . (left) The regions are marked on the reconstructed image and the corresponding values of g_s are extracted from the reconstruction. (right) We extract the contrast from the regions in the raw data collected by FERI and by conventional PINEM. Although the collection time in FERI (20s) is 21 times shorter than that of the PINEM image (420s), the features of the phonon-polariton near-field are already more visible in the FERI image. (b) Coherent amplification in the classical regime (electron energy spread wider than $\hbar\omega$), which is demonstrated in this work. The values from the table in (a) and an additional value are marked on the theoretical curve. The experimental parameters are used to draw the theory curves. (c) Coherent amplification in the quantum regime (electron energy spread narrower than $\hbar\omega$), showing prospects for additional amplification beyond the classical regime, achieving higher contrast for smaller values of g_s ⁸⁶.

The overall signal enhancement achieved by our FERI scheme has two contributions of a fundamentally different nature: the *coherent* nature of electron-field interactions, and the

coherence between the reference and the sample fields. To explain this contribution, we recall that the signal of conventional PINEM of an electron with velocity v moving along z depends on a dimensionless parameter $g(x, y) = \frac{q_e}{\hbar\omega} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz E_z(x, y, z) e^{-iz\omega/v}$ ^{88,89}, with q_e being the electron charge and ω the laser frequency. For weak fields E_s ($|g_s| \ll 1$), the electron image signal scales as $|g_s|^2$. The coherent amplification that FERI provides is based on the idea that a reference field E_r can be added up coherently to the signal without directly illuminating the sample. Instead, the interference is mediated *by the electron* as it is propagating between the fields. As a result, for weak fields $|g_s| \ll 1$, the electron image signal scales as $|g_s|$ (Methods M8), rather than $|g_s|^2$. Thus, FERI is beneficial for situations where strong fields are difficult to apply due to weak coupling or damage to the sample. A similar enhancement factor was suggested in several works on electron interactions^{55,90}. To the best of our knowledge, our work is the first to demonstrate the effect of free-electron coherent amplification experimentally.

The coherent amplification provided by FERI relative to conventional PINEM can be described analytically when assuming that the electron's initial energy distribution is Gaussian. When filtering only electrons with energy greater than E_{filter} , the contrast amplification factor is given by (Methods M8):

$$\frac{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(2(|g_r|)) - J_n^2(2(|g_r| + |g_s|))] \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right)}{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(0) - J_n^2(2|g_s|)] \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right)}, \quad (1)$$

where J_l are the Bessel functions of the first kind, ΔE is the electron energy spread and E_0 is the mean electron energy. Equation 1 shows a good qualitative agreement with our data, as shown in Fig. 4b. Expanding the amplification factor to powers of $|g_s|$ yields the $1/|g_s|$ scaling factor for weak fields, in accordance with free-electron quantum sensing protocols⁹⁰.

Our algorithm relies on the fact that scanning over the relative phase provides an arbitrary number of measurements for a fixed number of unknown variables. In fact, for each pixel, we need to find just two degrees-of-freedom, the amplitude and the phase, from a scan

over any number of relative phases. This type of over-constrained problem is common in interferometric reconstructions such as homodyne detection⁸⁵. However, unlike other interferometric techniques, the electron interaction with the field is highly nonlinear, which renders linear tools like the Radon transform generally inapplicable. The nonlinearity necessitates using the exact PINEM theory in the core of our algorithm (Methods M6).

We developed an optimization algorithm that solves the PINEM equations and finds the amplitude and phase for each pixel. The optimization problem is not convex (i.e., there are many local minima), so instead of gradient-descent-based methods, we create a heat-map and search for the global minima within it. Altogether, the over-constrained nature of the scheme enables extracting a good estimate of the ground truth (the correct near-field) for a wide range of parameters – as we show both experimentally and theoretically. The algorithm is described in detail in⁸⁶.

Discussion

When applying FERI theory in actual experiments, we separate between two cases: (1) electron energy spread ΔE larger than $\hbar\omega$ (classical regime, Fig. 4b), and (2) electron energy spread ΔE smaller than $\hbar\omega$ (quantum regime, Fig. 4c). Comparing the two regimes shows an interesting feature: the contrast in both PINEM and FERI is higher in the quantum regime, despite the ratio of the PINEM-FERI contrasts remaining approximately the same in both regimes. The advantage of the quantum regime lies in the fact that it is easier to distinguish electrons that absorbed or emitted even just one photon from those that did not change their energy. We note that Eq. 1 generalizes both regimes under a single formula (further details in Methods M8).

To estimate the minimal field amplitude E that is possible to image with FERI, consider that the PINEM parameter interaction strength satisfies $g \approx \frac{Eq_eL}{\hbar\omega}$ ^{88,89}, with L being an effective

interaction length between the electron and the field. For the phonon polaritons we observed, L is typically a few μm . We estimate the weaker features in Fig. 3 to have $g_s \sim 0.2$, corresponding to a field E of few kV/m or intensities around 1 W/cm^2 .

The distance between the electron modulation and the sample is known to have a critical role in determining the interaction results. Notable efforts for phase-dependent interactions in transmission electron microscopes aimed for pre-modulation have been made at the exact bunching distance before the sample^{59,81}. Such bunched electrons provide direct reading of the sub-cycle spatiotemporal dynamics of the field. However, this approach may not be feasible for imaging phonon polaritons due to their long wavelengths that necessitate a significantly longer bunching distance than the typical lengths available in electron microscopes. Our work bypassed this limit by showing that a proper data-analysis algorithm (as in FERI) can fully reconstruct the sub-cycle dynamics for arbitrary distances between the modulation and the sample. Our approach can now be directly applied to enhance current efforts for sub-cycle microscopy in the near-IR and visible regimes, replacing the restrictive pre-bunching distance by a simple data post-processing stage that reconstructs the same information.

It is important to differentiate the phase-resolved near-field imaging capabilities enabled by modulated electrons from the most established methods of phase-resolved near-field measurements. In particular, photo-emission electron microscopy (PEEM)⁹¹⁻⁹³ is based on the nonlinear response of the target sample, which becomes less efficient for low-energy photons as in the mid-IR. Hence, this approach is not easily applied to investigate phonon polaritons in 2D materials, which are typically present in the mid-IR or at lower photon energies. Moreover, PEEM is limited to probing phenomena near surfaces, unlike FERI, which is inherently sensitive to the bulk. This latter difference also distinguishes FERI from scattering-type scanning nearfield optical microscopy (sSNOM)^{72,94-96}. Generally, near-field measurements using scanning tips are well-established over wide spectral bandwidths and can

be performed as well with an ultrafast source^{72,95,96}. However, the reconstruction of the polaritonic field from the measurement is often limited by requiring precise modelling and assumptions on the tip-field interaction. More generally, unlike tip-based techniques that inevitably disturb the near-field, the electron probe can measure the near-field without altering it.

Outlook

The ability of FERI to measure the amplitude and phase of the fields also in the bulk of a sample opens a set of intriguing capabilities. For example, by making angle-dependent measurements, FERI can be used to make a full tomographic scan and extract the 3D profile of an electromagnetic mode. This would be a completely new type of measurement, not possible by other means. Another notable application arising from this combination of capabilities is imaging highly confined polaritons, such as acoustic graphene polaritons^{97,98}, which are highly laterally confined and can become practically inaccessible to surface techniques such as scanning near-field optical microscopy. Additionally, by resolving phase dynamics, FERI enables direct measurements of polaritonic vortices⁵⁰ and polaritonic chaos⁹⁹.

The coherently amplified sensitivity of FERI enables the study of deeply confined polaritons such as in picocavities and hBN cavities^{100–102}, that are otherwise undetectable due to their low coupling efficiency and limited interaction lengths. The sensitivity may also provide access to highly desired polariton nonlinearities in 2D, vdW, and phononic materials^{103–105}. Such nonlinearities are typically challenging to observe due to their small variation in polaritonic wavelengths. Moreover, FERI's ability to image low-intensity fields may open new modalities for imaging biological samples and other dose-sensitive materials^{5,106–108}. Enticing goals that could now be attempted include quantum materials, such as encapsulated 2D superconductors⁶² and others that were so far beyond reach. By using laser

modulation to increase the amount of information that can be extracted per single electron, FERI reduces the number of electrons needed to pass by the sample, thus minimizing radiation damage. From a fundamental perspective, coherent amplification of the intrinsic electron-photon interaction is also crucial for observing electron interactions with single photons or with vacuum fluctuations^{109–112}.

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Methods

1. Sample preparation

Samples were fabricated using viscoelastic polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) dry transfer techniques. In the fabrication process, we mechanically exfoliate isotopically pure $h^{11}\text{BN}$ crystals grown as detailed in¹¹³, on viscoelastic PDMS tapes. To reduce the amount of chemical residue and to conserve the hBN crystal, no tape was used in the exfoliation. Rather, exfoliation was performed directly with low retention PDMS (commercially available from GELPAK, X0 retention, in DGL or PF format). After the initial exfoliation steps, the PDMS was visibly covered with many hBN crystals, at which point a fresh PDMS sheet was used to pick up (and exfoliate further) a portion of the hBN. Further exfoliation using fresh pieces of PDMS was repeated until the typical flake thickness was estimated, based on optical microscope examination, to be close to the target thickness.

After 2-5 such rounds, a last round of exfoliation was performed directly on the stamp, by attaching and separating it to one of the hBN covered PDMS sheets. By controlling the speed of the exfoliation, especially in this last step, we change the prevalent physical process; at slower speeds, flakes tend to move from one PDMS to another and at higher speeds they tend to exfoliate, but at the risk that they apply strain and crack or break the flakes. To better estimate the thickness of the hBN flakes we performed EELS log-ratio measurements^{114,115} and obtained 40-50 nm for the investigated flake.

The target on which the hBN was dropped, was a 2-by-2 array of 10 μm circular holes (Extended Data Fig. 1) in a 50 nm-thick Si_3N_4 membrane (available commercially from Norcada Inc.), upon which a layer of Au (with a Ti seed layer) was thermally evaporated. Nominal thickness of the Au (Ti) is 10 nm (2 nm), calibrated by AFM measurements on a calibration chip.

Extended Data Fig. 1 | Sample images. (a,b) TEM images of the investigated hBN flake. The experimental results shown in the main text could be reproduced in different windows of the flake, however, the highlighted window (b) gave the best coupling efficiency and thus strongest signal. (c) Electron diffraction pattern of the hBN flake highlighted in (b), confirming that the whole flake is monocrystalline. (d) Optical microscope image of the investigated hBN flake. Different colors correspond to different hBN thicknesses and are formed due to optical interference in the hBN and substrate. The investigated window shows a uniform thickness.

To drop the flakes, the membrane was heated to 60 °C, after which the PDMS was slowly brought into contact with the membrane window. We constantly tracked the locations of the flake, membrane window, and contact front between the PDMS and the membrane's support substrate under an optical microscope. The PDMS was then lifted slowly, leaving the hBN attached to the Au layer. In some cases, if the flake appeared not to connect to the membrane, the temperature was raised up to 90 °C before the stamp was lifted. The regions of interest in the experiment were the pre-etched holes in the membrane. At these regions the hBN flake is free-standing, thereby minimizing electron losses in the material and reducing substrate-related losses of the phonon-polariton. Our experimental studies focused on one of these windows, indicated in Extended Data Fig. 1 below, where the quality of the particular hBN flake was superior. The other holes showed related polaritonic behavior, but with weaker laser coupling strength and less pronounced features. Multiple measurements with the same settings showed little variation in the acquired signal, indicating that the system is reproducible and that the flakes did not deteriorate over time.

2. Experimental setup

The measurements were performed in an ultrafast transmission electron microscope (UTEM) based on a JEOL JEM-2100 Plus TEM with a LaB₆ electron gun and acceleration voltage of 200 kV (Extended Data Fig. 2a-b). The UTEM operates as a pump–probe setup driven by a 40 W, 1030 nm, ~270 fs laser (Carbide, Light Conversion) operating at a 1 MHz repetition rate. The output of this laser is split into two pulses: one pulse is upconverted into 266 nm (UV) using two stages of second-harmonic generation and excites the LaB₆ cathode, generating single-electron probe pulses at the laser repetition rate. These electron pulses travel down the microscope column, passing the reference and sample interactions (see below), and are eventually measured by one of the installed electron detectors. The second pulse is converted into variable wavelengths in the IR range (in this work ~7-8 μm) through a difference frequency generation (DFG) process in an optical parametric amplifier (OPA, Orpheus, Light Conversion). This IR pulse is then split into two pulses (Extended Data Fig. 2a-b), one of them is used to excite the sample (sample interaction) and the other is used to excite a thin Aluminum film deposited on an electron-transparent Si₃N₄ membrane (Extended Data Fig. 2c). This membrane is positioned in the electron path, prior to the sample, and serves as the reference point of interaction in the photonic electron modulator (PELM) scheme.

Extended Data Fig. 2 | The UTEM setup and the PELM integration. UTEM illustration (a) and image (b) illustrating the microscope column, electron spectrometer and detectors, optical setup, and the integration of a modified Hard X-ray Aperture (HXA) at a post-condenser lens stage (PELM). The external knob of the HXA (a and b, left side) has two rigid positioning points with 5 mm lateral travel around them for positioning the reference interaction point with respect to the electron beam path. An electron-transparent thin-film sits at the place of the x-ray aperture and light enters from the optical access port on the opposite side of the column at a 20-degree angle above the horizon (dashed red line in b). Double illumination scheme (a and b, right side) implemented on the vertical board next to the UTEM. The IR laser beam is separated into two portions using a 50:50 beam splitter. One portion is guided towards the PELM (dashed red line in b), whereas the other portion is guided towards the sample (solid red line in b). (c) Image (left) and CAD model (right) of the modified HXA aperture connected to the platelet hosting the electron-transparent light-opaque metallic thin films for electron-light interaction. The platelet is made of Aluminum alloy, whereas the clamp is made of 0.15-mm-thick Beryllium Copper. One can observe two Si-window TEM grids (Norcada Inc.) which are coated with a 25-nm-thick Aluminum film deposited via thermal evaporation on a 10-nm-thick Si₃N₄ membrane. In each grid, nine slots are present to maximize the available points of interaction in case of local damage to one of the membranes. The platelet has also been cut at a specific angle allowing it to host a small metallic mirror able to reflect the light down the column towards the sample position (not used in the current work). The platelet, HXA and their integration were designed and performed in close collaboration with IDES, part of JEOL Ltd.

The temporal and spectral profiles of the IR laser pulse were characterized through an independent PINEM measurement on a metallic film, and using a grating spectrometer near the DFG stage, respectively. Noticeably, the IR pump pulse experiences some distortion along the ~5-meter optical path leading to the electron microscope column, which contributes to the observed chirp¹¹⁶. The temporal delays between the electron pulse and the sample interaction, and between the sample and reference interactions are controlled by two motorized stages, with

temporal step size of 10 fs and 1 fs, respectively, allowing sub-optical-cycle scanning of the sample and reference interaction temporal response.

The TM-polarized IR pulses are focused using two lenses positioned near the microscope column, reaching a spot size of $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$ and average power of 4-12 mW at the sample interaction, and a spot size of $\sim 500 \mu\text{m}$ and average power of 4-20 mW at the reference interaction. The average laser power absorbed by the sample is understood to be too low to induce significant heating of the sample, especially considering the phonon-polariton increased heat conductivity¹¹⁷, and is below hBN's intensity damage threshold.

The sample interaction laser pulse enters the UTEM column via a side entry port, situated at the sample plane (Extended Data Fig. 2a-b). At the side entry port, the laser pulse is focused via a lens and propagates perpendicular to the electron direction of motion (z), until reaching the sample. To prevent shadowing of the laser by the TEM grid and sample holder, our sample was tilted by 35 degrees counter-clockwise along the TEM holder rotation axis.

The reference interaction laser pulse enters the column above the sample interaction point, after passing through a lens, and propagates towards the Aluminum sample of the reference interaction at 20 degrees counter-clockwise with respect to the lateral plane (Extended Data Fig. 2a). The reference sample itself is tilted by 41 degrees counter-clockwise with respect to the same plane (Extended Data Fig. 2c). Both tilts are done along the same axis, which is orthogonal to the laser propagation. These tilt angles ensure that the electron and laser pulse are phase-matched on the reference interaction sample despite their different propagation velocities (a 200 keV electron travels at $0.7c$). Furthermore, the electron spot size on the reference interaction sample was intentionally kept as small as possible to ensure that the electron acquires a homogeneous phase over the entire area.

For the measurements with one point of interaction only, the Aluminum sample of the reference interaction was kept in the electron beam path, and only the laser illumination at that

interaction was blocked. The average laser excitation power of the reference and signal interactions was measured individually using two power meters, and was monitored routinely throughout the measurements. The lowest average laser excitation power we could detect using two points of interaction was around 2 mW (at a wavelength of 7000 nm, where the signal was most visible).

After the interaction with the excited membranes (reference and sample), the free-electron energy spectrum was measured using a post-column electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) system with a spectrometer dispersion of 0.1 eV (Gatan Inc.). The EELS system includes a slit for producing energy-filtered transmission electron microscopy (EFTEM) images. The measurements without a reference interaction were scanned for the best slit position such that only electrons which gained energy from the sample interaction were measured. Similarly, measurements with both interactions were scanned for a slit position such that only electrons which gained energy from both interactions were measured. The FWHM of the electron zero-loss peak (ZLP) without the interactions is 1.4-1.5 eV.

3. Image acquisition

The electron microscope images presented throughout the manuscript were acquired using a direct-detection camera (K2 Summit, Gatan Inc.) mounted on the EELS instrument. To enable a direct comparison between measurements carried using one-point and two-points of interaction, the sum of the exposure times of all the phase-scan images (21×20 s) matched the exposure time of the conventional PINEM image (420 s).

In all the acquired images, there exist several detector-related sources of noise. As a result, the detector software usually performs substantial automated image processing on the raw image data. However, to achieve better control of the data analysis, we have exported the raw data and performed all the image processing ourselves.

4. Correcting for 3D sample tilt using image processing

For quantitative analysis of the phonon-polariton properties, such as the phase velocity, one must first correct the sample tilt in space with respect to the propagation direction of the free-electrons. Due to the two-axes tilt, the raw data exhibits an oval instead of a circular shape. Extended Data Fig. 3 presents the procedure that corrects for the tilt and retrieves the original circular shape.

Extended Data Fig. 3 | Image post-processing revealing the phonon-polaritons properties. (a) The relative phase scan produces the FERI tilted raw measurements which are used to reconstruct the amplitude and phase **(b)**. **(c1-4)** The process for the ellipse estimation: **(c1)** convert the amplitude reconstructed image to black and white by thresholding. **(c2-3)** perform morphological image processing¹¹⁸. **(c4)** estimate the ellipse equation through connected component analysis. **(d)** Perform an affine transformation on the reconstructed images using the inverse of the estimated ellipse equation.

5. Comparison of PINEM and FERI

Extended Data Fig. 4 compares results of amplitude and phase reconstruction using FERI to the conventional images of PINEM, shown for different interaction strengths at the sample. The average interaction strengths over the entire image are estimated to be $|g_s| \approx [0.4, 0.8, 1.4]$ (estimated from an EELS measurement). The figure compares conventional PINEM to FERI amplitude imaging for the same electron dose on the sample per second per pixel.

One can see a clear amplification in the FERI amplitude imaging for different interaction strength, as predicted by theory (Fig. 4 of the main text). For the sake of completeness, we show that the amplification remains substantial even when further optimizing the filter parameter in PINEM while the FERI filtering is not necessarily optimized. Moreover, while conventional PINEM lacks phase information, FERI displays phase images for all the different interaction strengths. Overall, the FERI amplitude and phase imaging offer a significant improvement over conventional PINEM imaging.

Extended Data Fig. 4 | Phonon-polariton amplitude and phase reconstruction for different illumination intensities compared to conventional PINEM imaging. Data acquired using three different average interaction strengths over the entire image: $|g_s| \approx 0.4, 0.8, 1.4$, top to bottom, respectively. **(a)** conventional PINEM amplitude imaging for the three different interaction strengths and for different energy filtering (10 eV slit width, cutoff energy is marked at the bottom of each image), acquired for the same time-delay. **(b)** FERI amplitude imaging for the same electron dose on the sample. As predicted by theory (Fig. 4 of the main text), the largest amplification is seen for the weakest interaction strength. The right column shows FERI phase images for the different interaction strengths.

6. Free-electron Ramsey imaging (FERI): theoretical framework

At the core of PINEM lies the fundamental interaction between free-electrons and near-fields. Following typical approximations^{36,43,53,57,88,89,119–122}, the Hamiltonian describing the interaction between the electromagnetic field and the electron is given by $H = E_0 - i\hbar v \partial_z +$

$evE_z(x, y, z)/\omega$, where E_0 is the initial electron energy, v is the electron velocity, e is the fundamental charge, z is the electron propagation direction, $E_z(x, y, z)$ is the local electric near-field amplitude along z , and ω is the electromagnetic field fundamental frequency.

Previous works have derived a dimensionless parameter, $g = \frac{e}{\hbar\omega} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz E_z(x, y, z) e^{-\frac{iz\omega}{v}}$, that characterizes the interaction strength^{88,89}. In general, $g = g(x, y)$ is a complex number and a function of the transverse coordinates (x, y) . By measuring $g(x, y)$, one can in principle recover both the amplitude and the phase of the near-field $E_z(x, y)$, which in certain cases can suffice to reconstruct the full field information¹²³. The probability for the electron to change its energy by $l\hbar\omega$, where l is an integer, is given by $P_l = |J_l(2|g|)|^2$, where J_l is the l -th order Bessel function of the first kind. Furthermore, considering the electron energy spread ΔE , to be a gaussian profile $G_{\Delta E}(E)$, we rewrite the above probability as:

$$P(E) = \sum_l |J_l(2|g|)|^2 G_{\Delta E}(E - l\hbar\omega). \quad (1)$$

Applying this theory to FERI can be done by considering two points of interaction, thus we have $g = g_r + g_s$, where g_r and g_s are the interaction strengths of the reference and sample fields, respectively. The FERI theory can be directly generalized for cases where the distance between the two points of interaction is large (and hence the electron pulse dispersion must be accounted for). However, this is not necessary in our setup since the distance between the two interaction points is 37 mm, negligible compared to the Talbot distance^{124,125}, which is on the order of a few meters in the case of mid-IR. This allows us to neglect the electron pulse dispersion between the two points of interaction, and effectively interferes the reference and sample near-fields with each other via the electron pulse. The electron pulse is then sent through a dispersive magnetic prism and filtered in energy using a slit to measure only the part of the electron which gained energy in both interactions. By using Eq. 1 to build the energy filtered TEM (EFTEM) model, one will get:

$$M(x, y, t, \Delta\phi, E_{\text{slit}}, g_s(x, y)) = \int_{E_{\text{min}}}^{E_{\text{max}}} \sum_l G_{\Delta E}(E - \hbar\omega_l) \cdot |J_l(2|g_r(\Delta\phi) + g_s(x, y, t))|^2 dE, \quad (2)$$

where x, y are the sample spatial coordinates, t follows the evolution of the sample dynamics, $\Delta\phi$ is the relative phase between the two laser pulses inducing the two interactions, and $E_{\text{slit}} = [E_{\text{min}}, E_{\text{max}}]$ is the electron energy-filtering slit position. Repeating this measurement while varying the sample-reference relative phase $\Delta\phi$, using sub-cycle steps, allows us to generate a complete dataset (phase scan) which fully captures the near-field dynamics at the sample.

Our FERI technique⁸⁶ applies an algorithmic approach to reconstruct the phase and amplitude of the field at the sample from the energy filtered measurements of the phase scan (Extended Data Fig. 5), The reconstruction is based on the following FERI optimization expression:

$$\underset{|g_s(x,y)|, \angle g_s(x,y)}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_i |Y_i - M(x, y, t, \Delta\phi_i, E_{\text{slit}}, g_s(x, y))|^2, \quad (3)$$

where Y_i is the i -th measurement of the phase scan, M is the measurement model (see Eq. (2)), and the reconstructed quantities are the amplitude $|g_s(x, y)|$ and phase $\angle g_s(x, y)$ of the sample field for each point in space independently.

Notably, this optimization expression is not convex, i.e., it exhibits multiple local minima, and it is well known that gradient descent methods can easily converge to a local minimum. To solve this issue, the minimization procedure scans over the relative phase $\Delta\phi$, and thanks to the low variable space (solving only for $|g_s|, \angle g_s$), we are able create a heatmap and perform an exhaustive search, where finding the global minimum is guaranteed (Extended Data Fig. 5a3).

Extended Data Fig. 5 | The optimization procedure used in FERI. Visualization (a) and block scheme (b) of the optimization process. The free-electrons are pre-modulated by a reference field before they probe the sample field and are energy-filtered to produce electron distribution measurements for each relative phase (a1). For each transverse pixel (x, y) , several heat-maps are generated, for different relative phases between the reference and signal fields (a2). The summed joint heat-map (a3) enables the accurate estimate of the amplitude and phase for each pixel. (c) The amplitude and phase reconstruction after optimizing using all the relative phases and for all the pixels.

7. Simulating phonon-polariton dynamics

In this section, we present the modeling of the phonon-polaritons (PhP) and their excitation by a laser pulse used in our simulations. We assume the laser excites multiple electric dipoles on the circular edges of the sample, with the relative phase and orientation of each dipole following the laser's polarization and propagation direction. We then find the PhP electric field pattern each dipole creates using the dyadic Green's function of a 45-nm-thick hBN sheet and assuming scattering boundary conditions.

For convenience, we set our axes with respect to the micro-drum such that the z -axis is the hBN surface normal. We consider a single-frequency plane wave exciting a set of dipoles along the edge of the sample. The incoming plane wave has the following electric field:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = E_0 (\cos(\alpha) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_1 + e^{i\beta} \sin(\alpha) \hat{\mathbf{e}}_2) e^{-i\frac{\omega}{c}(\sin(\theta) \cos(\varphi)x + \sin(\theta) \sin(\varphi)y - \cos(\theta)z)}, \quad (4)$$

where θ (φ) is the propagation angle with respect to the z (x) axis. The polarizations are $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_1 = \sin(\varphi) \hat{\mathbf{x}} - \cos(\varphi) \hat{\mathbf{y}}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{e}}_2 = \cos(\theta) \cos(\varphi) \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\varphi) \hat{\mathbf{y}} + \sin(\theta) \hat{\mathbf{z}}$. We note that the phase and polarization of the field break the circular symmetry in our simulations, which allows the center of the resulting PhP wave to move from the center of the sample. Notably,

these polarizations cannot be addressed completely as TE and TM since there is no translational symmetry in any of the directions. As a result, both polarizations can excite the TM polarized PhPs, which can be measured by the electron.

The TM polarization of the PhPs means that they can only be excited by dipoles perpendicular to the edge. That is, assuming a linear polarizability α and a circular boundary, the induced dipole along the edge is written as $\mathbf{p}_{\text{in}} = \alpha[(\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}(\phi, R, z = 0) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}})\hat{\mathbf{r}} + (\mathbf{E}_{\text{in}}(\phi, R, z = 0) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{z}})\hat{\mathbf{z}}]$. Here the electric field is written in cylindrical coordinates, where R is the radius of our sample, and ϕ is the azimuthal angle. We can rewrite the induced dipole at each angle ϕ along the edges of our sample as:

$$\mathbf{p} \propto e^{-i\frac{\omega}{c}(\sin(\theta)\cos(\phi)R\cos\phi + \sin(\theta)\sin(\phi)R\sin\phi)} \cdot \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cos(\alpha) [\sin(\phi)\cos\phi\hat{\mathbf{r}} - \cos(\phi)\sin\phi\hat{\mathbf{r}}] + \\ + e^{i\beta}\sin(\alpha) [\cos(\theta)\sin(\phi)\sin\phi\hat{\mathbf{r}} + \cos(\theta)\cos(\phi)\cos\phi\hat{\mathbf{r}} + \sin(\theta)\hat{\mathbf{z}}] \end{array} \right\}. \quad (5)$$

Next, we connect the induced dipoles and the PhP electric field produced in the sample. For a set of dipoles, this connection is done using the Dyadic Green's function \vec{G} , through:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{php}}(\mathbf{r}; \omega) = \int d\mathbf{r}_s \vec{G}(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{r}_s; \omega) \mathbf{p}_{\text{in}}(\mathbf{r}_s; \omega). \quad (6)$$

For an infinite slab, the Green's function component that excites E_z takes the form of

$$\begin{aligned} & G_{zx}^{\text{inf}}(x, y, z = 0, x_s, y_s, z' = 0; \omega) \\ &= \frac{ic^2}{8\pi^2\omega^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_x dq_y q_x e^{-iq_y(y-y_s)} e^{-iq_x(x-x_s)} r_p(q, \omega) \\ & G_{zy}^{\text{inf}}(x, y, z = 0, x_s, y_s, z' = 0; \omega) \\ &= \frac{ic^2}{8\pi^2\omega^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_x dq_y q_y e^{-iq_y(y-y_s)} e^{-iq_x(x-x_s)} r_p(q, \omega) \\ & G_{zz}^{\text{inf}}(x, y, z = 0, x_s, y_s, z' = 0; \omega) \\ &= \frac{ic^2}{8\pi^2\omega^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dq_x dq_y \frac{q^2}{k_z} e^{-iq_y(y-y_s)} e^{-iq_x(x-x_s)} r_p(q, \omega) \end{aligned}$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum and $k_z = \sqrt{\frac{\omega^2}{c^2} - q^2}$. The p-polarized reflection coefficient of the hBN slab $r_p(q, \omega)$ is a function of the in-plane momentum $q = \sqrt{q_x^2 + q_y^2}$ and the frequency ω , incorporating the PhP dispersion (shown in Fig. 3 of the main text). These Green's functions convert the dispersion in momentum space to spatial responses. The assumption of scattering boundary condition implies that the resulting interference pattern is achieved by summing up the contributions of many dipoles along the surface without considering reflections.

The analysis described here was used to generate the simulated results in Fig.1 of the main text. For simplicity our simulation approximated the boundary conditions to be scattering, rather than mixed scattering-reflecting. Nevertheless, the simulation captures the general shape and features of the wave-pattern in the experiment and is used to illustrate the basic principles of the underlying physics.

8. Coherent amplification in FERI: calculation of the amplification factor

In this section, we derive the contrast amplification formulas for PINEM and FERI. We start from the quantum electron regime, where the energy spread of the electron is significantly smaller than the light quanta ($\sigma_E \ll \hbar\omega$) such that we approximate the electron energy distribution to be a delta function centered around the initial electron energy E_0 . We consider a total interaction g that is composed of a reference interaction and a sample interaction such that $g = g_s + g_r$. The energy distribution of the electron is thus given by the typical PINEM formula:

$$P(E) = \sum_n J_n^2(2|g|)\delta(E - E_0 - n\hbar\omega). \quad (7)$$

We then filter the electron energy such that the signal contains only electrons that have energy higher than E_{filter} . In this case, the signal per electron is given by:

$$\text{Signal} = \sum_{n \text{ s.t. } E_0 + n\hbar\omega > E_{\text{filter}}} J_n^2(2|g|). \quad (8)$$

When the ZLP of the electron is wide the amplitude of the electron should be convoluted with a Gaussian. However, in the “classical ensemble” regime where the incoherent broadening of the electron is wider than the photon quanta, all the interferences arising from the different Bessel functions wash out and we can convolve the probability density with the ZLP width instead of the amplitude¹²⁶. In this case, if the electron energy spread is given by ΔE , the final energy spectrum is given by:

$$P(E) = \sum_n \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\Delta E}} J_n^2(2|g|) e^{-\frac{(E-E_0-n\hbar\omega)^2}{2\Delta E^2}}. \quad (9)$$

The signal is filtered such that only electrons with energy greater than E_{filter} are accounted for. The filtered signal per electron is then calculated by integrating over the energy probability density:

$$\frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} J_n^2(2|g|) \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right). \quad (10)$$

Below the saturation zone of PINEM [67] the signal increases with g . We assume that the maximum field on the sample results when the interaction strength $g = g_s$, and the minimum field results when the interaction strength $g = 0$. In this case, the contrast in conventional PINEM is given by the difference between the signal with $g = g_s$ and $g = 0$:

$$\text{Contrast}_{\text{PINEM}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(0) - J_n^2(2|g|)]. \quad (11)$$

In FERI the interaction strength is given by $g = g_r + g_s$. To exemplify the enhancement, we compare the situation when there is no field on the sample ($|g| = |g_r|$) and the case where the sample field and the reference field constructively interfere $|g| = |g_r| + |g_s|$. In this case, the contrast given in a FERI experiment is:

$$\text{Contrast}_{\text{FERI}} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(2|g_r|) - J_n^2(2(|g_r| + |g_s|))] \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right). \quad (12)$$

By dividing the two contrast formulas we can get the total amplification formula presented in the main text:

$$\text{Amplification} = \frac{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(2|g_r|) - J_n^2(2(|g_r| + |g_s|))] \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right)}{\sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} [J_n^2(0) - J_n^2(2|g|)] \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right)}. \quad (13)$$

To understand the formula better it is valuable to look at the behavior in the limit of $|g_s| \ll 1$.

We look separately at the denominator and numerator and Taylor expand them to the lowest non-vanishing order. In this case the denominator reads:

$$|g_s|^2 \cdot \left[2 \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right) - \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right) - \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 + \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right) \right]. \quad (14)$$

While the numerator reads:

$$\sum_n 2|g_s| \cdot J_n(2|g_r|)(J_{n-1}(2|g_r|) - J_{n+1}(2|g_r|)) \cdot \text{erf}\left(\frac{E_{\text{filter}} - E_0 - n \cdot \hbar\omega}{\sqrt{2}\Delta E}\right). \quad (15)$$

The critical part here is that the numerator scales linearly with $|g_s|$ while the denominator scales quadratically. This shows us how the interferometric information give rise to $\frac{1}{|g_s|}$ amplification for weak fields, this amplification is the core of the improved imaging sensitivity we present in this work.

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